

Working on a Dream: Publishing and Linking Belgian Person Observations using Citizen Science

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Updated Abstract (short)

A plethora of volunteer projects aim to make Belgian historic sources of person observations searchable in the online environment of the State Archives. However, these projects are scattered, incomplete and of varying quality. Access to the entire IIF-collection of scans is restricted and the link between person data and scans was lost. Meanwhile, Belgium is lagging behind in reconstructing historical life courses compared to the Netherlands, even though the sources are similar. The Persons in Contact (PiCo) ontology can support the standardisation and publication of historical person data as Linked Data. We propose working on basic infrastructure to model and link data into person reconstructions, and correct and validate information automatically or manually.

Abstract

A plethora of volunteer projects aim to make Belgian historic sources of person observations searchable. However, these projects are scattered and unconnected, which has resulted in data that is searchable but not available in its entirety, sometimes inaccessible, and definitely not interoperable. Meanwhile, Belgium is lagging behind in reconstructing historical life courses compared to the Netherlands, even though the sources are similar. This is due to a lack of funding at the level of state archives and missing coordination by an organisational partner who is held responsible. Furthermore, previous initiatives did not agree upon a common data model to exchange information and reuse software from other projects.

Fortunately, we do not need to reinvent the wheel and can learn from previous projects across the border and existing research incorporating citizen science. At the OpenLabs conference on *Creating Knowledge through Participatory Research* the organizers identified the primary methodological challenge as designing research methods to increase participation while ensuring data quality and validity, balancing openness whether as open data or open access research with maintaining high research standards. During the keynote, Alain Kaufmann, embedded participatory research within the EU guidelines for responsible research and innovation:

Responsible Research and Innovation is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products (in order to allow a proper embedding of scientific and technological advances in our society). – (EC & Schomberg, 2011, p.9).

While historic data may be less suitable as a marketable product, the current solution to making Belgian historical person data available is far from ideal.

Why FamilySearch is not an ideal solution

At first glance, FamilySearch is a logical partner as they have access to one of the largest collections of historical person records in the world. This collection encompasses most countries in the world and is very popular among genealogists. Moreover, FamilySearch has a proven track record of working together with researchers who wish to reconstruct life courses (Price et al., 2021; Ruggles, 2023). For each of these parties, the collaboration with FamilySearch has proven to be mutually beneficial, as they were able to test matching algorithms or release demographic datasets and did not have to create and maintain an infrastructure to store the data.

However, a major disadvantage to working together with FamilySearch is that the research institutions do not own the data and are not free to share it with others. This means that research is always to a certain extent unverifiable and irreproducible. Moreover, the enriched data and reconstructed life courses are commodified, meaning that genealogists and other interested parties cannot access any data produced by collective efforts without paying a membership fee. This helps create a monopoly for FamilySearch as they can combine an advantage in terms of the services for genealogists, with an information advantage over their competitors.

At the International Forum for Public History (IFPH), Catherine Fletcher (2024) discussed the financial dynamics of public history in *Follow the Money*. She dissected public history as an activity **by, with and for** the public. History by the public is community-produced as a collective, while history with the public is co-produced history. History for the public is produced for public consumption but public input is indirect and mediated.

Catherine Fletcher then distinguished a continuum of public history by funding from private to public sources. Private funding is a highly commercial, commodified version of history. In the middle we find publicly subsidized history for which there is some charge to users. Public history is then characterized by voluntary community history groups, neither charging members nor making a profit. Issues that arise is what is public history and how can private history be public? Privately digitized public records for instance create new barriers of access.

Creating a workflow and supporting infrastructure

Before we can even start thinking about a workflow to digitize the entirety of person observations in historical sources such as the civil registry or population registry, we need an inventory of available sources and what has been scanned. The state archive of Belgium

(*Rijksarchief*) has a searchable database of persons which returns 13,389,233 search results without any filters, which could point to 13 million person observations that have been indexed with varying quality by volunteers at local archives or in previous research projects.

In this exploratory phase the challenges lie in obtaining high-quality image material, especially due to the existing partnership between FamilySearch and the state archive; setting up a constructive partnership with the state archive to support the project and host the resulting data; and selecting an interesting research case study to test out the workflow and infrastructure.

We can build upon the experience of the Center for Family History in the Netherlands (CBG) in developing a linked data vocabulary Persons in Context (PiCo) to standardise historical person observations to make the already indexed person observations available to researchers as linked data. Additionally, we can build upon the expertise of The Quetelet Centre at Ghent University has ample experience in setting up a successful citizen science project with SOS Antwerp. Finally, on the Flemish side, CLARIAH-VL(+) is working on expanding an existing crowdsourcing tool to annotate, transcribe, and validate historical sources.

Through the funding of CLARIAH-VL, the digital tool Madoc was developed by Digirati. Madoc harnesses the strengths of the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) in combining high-quality images and metadata into single manifests that can be hosted and reused across platforms. Madoc also includes the possibility to build capture models linked to existing vocabularies to directly transcribe and enter relevant metadata according to linked data standards. Through Madoc, you can set up crowdsourcing projects that allow citizen scientists to annotate them, whilst maintaining a link between the image and annotations. Both the annotations and images are compliant with the IIIF standard. Given its crowdsourcing functionalities, and compliance with internationally used image and annotation standards, Madoc provides a valuable option to enrich the high-quality image material. Once citizen scientists start annotating scans of historical sources containing person observations, researchers and other specialists can validate or correct the digitised person observations before we export the data.

Once a substantial linked data set is available, we want to interlink Belgian person observations to support demographic research. We can support interlinking by building on an experiment with the burgerLinker software developed by the Dutch infrastructure project CLARIAH to interlink person observations from multiple sources into life courses. Since the interlinking should also be validated, we can evaluate the proof of concept of the civil registries reconstitutions cleaner (C2RC) and test the interface with citizen scientists according to user experience (UX) design principles.

At the DH BeNeLux, we wish to present an overview of existing efforts to digitise historical person records and how those individual efforts can come together. The conference is a place where relevant experts and stakeholders meet and seems like a logical choice to start working on an (inter)national framework.

Literature

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